

**DECEPTIVE ADVERTISING AND COVENANT UNIVERSITY STUDENTS'
PERCEPTION OF JENNY'S GLOW ADVERTS**

BY

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that Nkenang Uinction Gabriel, a student in the Department of Mass Communication, with the matriculation number 18BE023749, has satisfactorily completed the requirements for this research work, for the Degree of Bachelor of Science (BSc.) in Mass Communication. The work contained in this project is original, and has not, to the best of our knowledge, been submitted in part or full for any diploma or degree in this or any other university.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to God Almighty the giver of strength and hope. The one who has guided and blessed me with grace during the course of this research work. I also dedicate this project to my supportive parents, and also my supervisor who guided me through this work.

thank you for believing in me.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title page.....	I
Certification.....	II
Dedication.....	III
Acknowledgement.....	IV
Table of contents.....	VI
Abstract.....	X

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study.....	1
1.2 Statement of the problem.....	3
1.3 Objectives of the study.....	4
1.4 Research questions.....	5
1.5 Significance of study.....	5
1.6 Scope of the study.....	6
1.7 Operational definition of terms.....	6

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview of Advertising.....	8
2.2 Persuasive Nature of Advertising.....	9
2.3 Women and Skincare.....	10
2.4 Women’s Vulnerability.....	11
2.5 Women’s perception.....	11
2.6 Organic Skincare Products.....	12
2.7 Deceptive Advertising.....	14
2.7.1 Types and Tactics of Deceptive Advertisement.....	17
2.8 Analysis of Deceptive Advertising in the Skincare and Cosmetic Industry.....	21

2.9 Skincare Products.....	23
2.10 History of Cosmetic Skincare Advertising.....	24
2.11.1 Consumer Testimonials.....	25
2.11.2 Before-and-after Photo Claims.....	26
2.12 Practice of Deceptive Advertising in Skincare Products.....	26
2.13 Consumer’s Susceptibility and Perception to Deceptive Advertising.....	28
2.14 Understanding Consumer Buying Behavior and Purchase Decision Process.....	31
2.15 Theoretical Framework.....	34
2.15.1 Perception Theory.....	34
2.16 Implication of the Theory.....	35
2.17 Empirical Framework.....	36
2.18 Gaps to Fill.....	39

CHAPTER THREE: METHOD OF STUDY

3.1 Research Design.....	40
3.2 Population of the Study.....	40
3.3 Sample Size.....	40
3.4 Sampling Technique.....	41
3.5 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument.....	41

3.6 Method of Data Collection.....	41
3.7 Method of Data Analysis.....	42
CHAPTER 4: RESULTS	
4.1 Data Presentation and Analysis.....	43
4.2 Discussion of findings.....	59
CHAPTER 5: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
5.1 Summary.....	64
5.2 Conclusion.....	65
5.3 Recommendations.....	65
5.4 Limitations of the study.....	66
5.5 Suggestions for Further Studies.....	66
REFERENCES.....	67
APPENDIX I.....	70

ABSTRACT

Advertising is the most popular means of reaching potential customers with information about a product. The trend of using deception in advertising has been increasing since 2000. Nowadays, most companies and advertising agencies use misleading and colored information to make exaggerated claims to influence the consumers buying decision especially when it comes to skincare products. Hence, this study seeks to assess the perception of Covenant University female students towards Jenny's glow skincare product advertisement and to determine the level of knowledge of Covenant University female students towards Jenny's glow skincare product deceptive advertisements. The study was anchored on the perception theory. Using purposive and quota sampling technique, data was collected via questionnaire from 348 Covenant University female students and then analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The findings from this study revealed that they have heard, read or seen deceptive adverts before. In addition to this, aside being knowledgeable about these deceptive adverts, they have had first-hand experiences of deceptive adverts where they have been made to make purchase of products due to the adverts placed, only to discover that the product didn't meet the expectations from the adverts. This study also reveals that participants have been well exposed to

Jenny's Glow advertisements and it also shows that the perception of Covenant University students on Jenny's Glow adverts is on the negative side. This shows that the perception of Covenant University female students towards Jenny's Glow adverts is negative.

Keywords: *Deceptive advertising, perception, Jenny's Glow, Adverts.*

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The most common method of informing potential clients about a product is through advertising (Kariyawasam & Wigley, 2017). Marketing is a tool used to help firms expand. The notion of marketing combines elements from a number of academic disciplines, including sociology, economics, aesthetics, and psychology (Doborji & Hamed, 2016). Each person interprets advertising information differently, and consumers are never given information that is entirely objective.

Advertising is a powerful tool in the modern society that provides numerous benefits to organizations from the different sectors in the society including commercial, agricultural, banking, medicine among others. Several organizations have taken advantage of this still-evolving concept because of their awareness of the impact and relevance it has on the society (Dhaliwal, 2016).

According to Bhuyan (2017), advertising is a communication idea used to encourage and persuade a carefully chosen audience to do an action. This action could be a purchasing activity or an inculcating action. Advertising is used because it is well-known to play a significant role in both the economic growth of the advertiser and society at large. It also benefits various businesses by giving them a competitive edge.

False information can cause an unacceptable number of individuals to use it to make bad decisions. False information refers to the misrepresentation of the facts (Doborji & Hamed, 2016).

According to Muzahidul (2021), misleading advertising is currently one of the most talked-about and important issues in the globe. In any industry, it has become more than just a standard procedure. Businesses are moving away from moral concerns. The majority of marketers just have financial success in mind. In the commercial world, advertising has been very important in reaching clients more effectively and efficiently. From commercials, people can learn about high-quality items and their constituents. Deceptive advertising is a tactic used by multinational, international, and local businesses to market their goods, directly influencing consumer purchasing decisions. To boost sales, they provide inaccurate, deceptive, and biased information regarding the caliber of their goods. Advertisers disseminate deceptive, false, and fraudulent

information via TV, radio, print, outdoor, internet, and other media. Marketers have a direct impact on consumers' purchase decisions through these mediums and incorrect information.

Consumers are impacted by advertisers who use deceptive or inaccurate advertising. This occurs when customers are unfairly pushed to accept the promotional messages, clouding their judgment. Consumers who are subjected to deceptive advertising are either forced to pay more or for goods of lower quality than they had intended or they are led to choose the incorrect good or service (Kariyawasam & Wigley, 2017). By implying that the good or service has special attributes, such marketing violate consumers' interests. Additionally, they influence customers, making them more gullible and less likely to make wise decisions. The majority of the time, dishonest or deceptive advertising is prohibited by advertising restrictions. It is prohibited to give false information about a product's composition, manufacturing process, cost, or country of origin.

However, Jenny's Glow is used for this study because it is well-known and widely reached especially by youths and it is a chemical skincare brand that claims to be organic.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Sundarsan (2007) asserts that the role of advertising is essentially to fulfill the traditional desire of forms to reach the ever-increasing population so their products may receive optimum exposure. Online advertisers are in a hurry to attract the attention of their digital audience. Consequently, leading to an oversaturation of the online advertising world, such desperation has led to the propagation of untrue, misleading, inaccurate, as well as incomplete information, about

products and services thereby, leading to the purchase of such (Mccoy, Everard, Polak, & Galletta, 2007).

Women account for 70 to 80 percent of all consumer purchases. EY 1989, a worldwide professional services firm, projects that by 2018, women would earn \$18 trillion globally (Bridget Brennan 2016). In the course of designing for skincare companies, advertising agencies coin deceptive messages to help attract attention and patronage to skincare products. Consumers are bombarded with numerous commercials that encourage them to purchase cosmetics. Because females/women are the most influential consumers and the most lucrative target market for the cosmetics sector, the study focuses on Covenant University's female students. By providing incorrect information, advertisers harm customers and undermine the market's well-functioning structure. Since 2000, deceptive advertising practices have become more prevalent. Nowadays, the majority of businesses and advertising firms make inflated promises to sway consumers' purchasing decisions by using misleading and colored information. They believe that targeting women with their products will increase their profits, which has an adverse effect on both the women and society as a whole. Women's exploitation, persuading customers to purchase a product without adequately educating them about it, deceptive advertising that makes false claims, and other behaviors that potentially contribute to the moral decline of society are some actions that are extremely unethical. It is now urgently necessary to pay attention to this issue and increase consumer awareness of misleading advertising, especially among women, so that they can have the right to unaltered information and feel satisfied with their purchases.

While several studies have been done on the deceptive nature of skincare products, there are little studies in the Nigerian context on skincare advertisement in relation to Covenant University female students' perception and there is also no study on the deceptive nature of "Jenny's Glow".

This study therefore seeks to determine on one hand, the existence of deceptive skincare advertisements and on the other hand knowledge, exposure and perception of Covenant University female students towards deceptive skincare advertisements, Jenny's Glow precisely.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives are to;

- i. To investigate the exposure of Covenant University female students to Jenny's glow advertisement.
- ii. To assess the perception of Covenant University female students towards Jenny's glow advertisement.
- iii. To determine the level of knowledge of Covenant University female students towards Jenny's glow deceptive advertisements.
- iv. To investigate the consequences of these deceptive adverts on Covenant University female students.
- v. To suggest some recommendations and solutions to avoid deceptive advertising of Jenny's glow.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. To what extent have Covenant University female students been exposed to Jenny's glow advertisement?

- ii. What is the perception of Covenant University female students towards Jenny's glow advertisement?
- iii. What is the knowledge of Covenant University female students towards Jenny's glow advertisement?
- iv. What are the consequences of deceptive skincare products adverts on Covenant University female students?
- v. What are the solutions and recommendations that could be proffered to avoid deceptive advertising of Jenny's glow?

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Empirically, this study will offer information on misleading skincare product marketing, assisting scholars in understanding the topic. This research also may benefit researchers, who wish to carry out a study related to deceptive advertising in respect to the audience perception. The findings and recommendations of this study would assist advertisers and advertising agencies in the implementation and re-evaluation of their advertising campaigns. Also, the research would contribute to the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3 which aims at achieving 'good health and wellbeing'.

1.6 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

There are various forms of advertising and different brands of skincare products. This study is therefore limited to deceptive advertising and women's perception towards Jenny's Glow. It does

not concern other aspects of advertising such as social media or any organic skincare product other than Jenny's Glow.

1.7 OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF TERMS

- i. **Advertising:** It means an announcement or a paid form of promotion that aims at raising awareness, showing the attractive features of the skincare product or service, and persuading the consumers to take purchase action. This has to be done through selected media.
- ii. **Consumers:** They are the end users of the production chain, the people that the product is made for. In this context, they refer to people who skincare products adverts are intended for.
- iii. **Deception:** In this study, deception will mean persuading prospective consumers of organic skincare products (Jenny's Glow) to buy such products, using false and misleading information.
- iv. **Perception:** In this context, it shall be seen from the angle of the subjective idea and views that a person or group of people have about a particular element or subject.
- v. **Product:** It is a feasible object that is created and produced to satisfy a need. From the perspective of this study, it refers to objects created for skincare products.
- vi. **Covenant University students:** Female students at Covenant University between the ages of 15 and 30 will be used for the study since they are more likely to be concerned with their appearance.

- vii. **Jenny's Glow:** Jenny's glow is a skincare brand that was created in 2017 by Igbinoba Jennifer, popularly known as Jenny's Glow. It is one of the most successful Nigerian Skin care and beauty brand. It is located in 1st floor, Brasas'r, Admiralty Way, Eti-Osa, Lagos. It also has branches in Abuja, Port-Harcourt and Benin.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter is concerned with related literature and as such the review is based on literature on conceptual review, review of studies as well as the theoretical framework. The sources of literature review are gotten from textbook on advertising, mass media, encyclopedia and the internet.

2.1 OVERVIEW OF ADVERTISING

According to Ahmed and Saira (2019), the main goal of advertisers is to acquire valuable consumers by influencing their opinions, expertise, and purchasing habits. Because of this,

advertisements serve as instruments for educating and persuading the general public to buy the commodity or service being offered. Advertising as a process, is said to be complete when the advertiser creates awareness in the minds of potential buyers, about the products or services through the best and available advertising medium, either broadcast, print or the new media.

Zia (2016) emphasizes that advertising is a paid form of message and adds that in advertising, the advertisers communicate information that is aimed at persuading the audience about a product or service, and its means of production. Advertising is one major marketing activity that aims at informing and persuading, which is beneficial for the demand and supply of a product and service. However, it has other benefits like the societal benefit of building culture, changing mind-sets, and influencing the thinking pattern of members of the society; giving an ethical, moral and value orientation.

In the modern world, advertising is a technique for persuasion that may be used in a variety of ways, from subtle and light persuasions to aggressive enforcement of non-respecting interests and presented demands in order to benefit both the firm and the audience. In order to benefit the audience and appeal to a wider audience, advertisements use amusing or educational features. The practice of advertising has gained popularity and permeated everyday life. It has gained societal importance and has a straightforward but powerful picture representation that is purposefully used by the advertiser. This representation has an effect on the audience; this effect may be weak or strong, and it may have an impact on the conscious or unconscious mind. This is why the subject of psychological manipulation is critical in the advertising process and in the advertising industry; it is a highly researched area, as it is important and beneficial to the process. The most important and crucial factor in influencing consumer behavior to make a purchase of a good or service is advertising. Informing the audience about the goods or services that the

advertising company produces, as well as basic information about the advertiser, is one of the main purposes of advertising. Adverts are very common tools, and new and creative ways are being employed everyday so as to allow advertisers to achieve the ultimate goal – which is to persuade the potential customers to take action successfully. For this reason, advertisers adopt persuasive techniques messages, as it is a major feature of advertising (Zia, 2016).

2.2 PERSUASIVE NATURE OF ADVERTISING

The definition of Zia (2016) explains that advertisers communicate information that is aimed at informing and persuading the audience about a product or service, and its means of production. One of the major characteristics of advertising is its persuasive nature; the end goal of advertising is to persuade the audience successfully, and this is why in developing the advertising messages, advertisers create content in order to influence the consumers into taking a purchase decision on the product of service being advertised.

Advertisers adopt psychology theories in order to persuade consumers. This has been proven over time to have caused an influence in purchase motivation. A major role in the advertising process is played by perception of consumers, and this is why an adept knowledge on psychology is essential in formulating a persuasive message (Baryshnikova, 2017).

2.3 WOMEN AND SKINCARE

Women who feel compelled to maintain a certain appearance are frequently willing to sacrifice long-term skin health for immediate and quick radiance. Additionally, producing a product with immediate results is simpler than creating one with long-term advantages. For these reasons, manufacturers frequently neglect to carefully consider the implications of the substances they

utilize. Women value skincare and cosmetics highly as consumers in general. Every woman aspires to be stunning. Women's minds have changed, and they are now more concerned with appearance and beauty. Women over 60 years old still like to appear young and beautiful. They are interested in anti-aging goods for themselves. They are aware of every component that has an impact on skin. This study aims to demonstrate the perception and importance of skincare products to women, Covenant University female students especially.

2.4 WOMEN'S VULNERABILITY

Vulnerability refers to "the characteristic or state of being exposed to the prospect of being attacked or damaged, either physically or emotionally". A window of vulnerability (WOV) is a period of time during which protective mechanisms are reduced, weakened, or nonexistent (Wikipedia).

When using skincare products, women go through a lot. Many skincare and cosmetic products contain chemicals and synthetic components, which can have a number of unfavorable side effects, particularly for women with sensitive skin and those who are susceptible to allergic responses.

According to a 2012 article by Ann Mane Britton titled "THE BEAUTY INDUSTRY'S INFLUENCE ON WOMEN IN SOCIETY," generating commercials with unrealistic images of beauty has caused anxiety, low self-esteem, and low self-confidence in many women. The majority of these negative emotions stem from dissatisfaction with one's appearance and body. It has also been demonstrated that college women commonly use cosmetics, are aware about the cosmetics industry, and that just a small number of personal criteria affect women's cosmetic tastes.

2.5 WOMEN'S PERCEPTION

Women's perceptions of brand personality in relation to women's facial appearance and cosmetic use were examined by Guthrie, Kim, and Jung in 2008. Sarla Jayesh and Manjrekar Pradip (2014), “TO STUDY THE PERCEPTION OF WOMEN AS CUSTOMERS TOWARDS BEAUTY SERVICE IN WESTERN MUMBAI”, according to her Women are particularly self-conscious about their appearance, so marketers have created a variety of options to change appearance. Even while the desire to look better hasn't changed, you now have access to more advanced tools than in the past. Beauty services were developed since there was such a big need for them. The typical methods and tools from older periods have now been modernized and altered for use.

2.6 ORGANIC SKINCARE PRODUCTS

Over the past few decades, the market for organic skincare products has expanded. The increased interest in this kind of product is a result of the growing environmental and health-related anxiety among consumers. Consumers not only value the use of sustainable chemicals in cosmetic formulations, but they are also concerned about the pollution that plastic consumption causes, which is forcing industry to reinvent themselves and reconsider the materials used in packaging. The fact that the consumer is using a sustainable product in addition to helping to preserve the environment is what influences people to buy organic cosmetics the most. As a result of the rising demand for organic cosmetics, brands are becoming more concerned about the organic issue, the reduction of animal-derived ingredients, and the updating of the criteria needed to certify a cosmetic as natural or organic. Due to the few studies available in this field, the need of clarifying the definitions and ideas of natural and organic cosmetics is clear, in order to provide with reliable information for the cosmetic business. According to American Academy of Dermatology (www.aad.org/public/kids/skin), skin comprises the largest organ of human body

with over 20 vital physiological functions. Skin which is a physical barrier to withstand pressure and trauma, recognize sensations and pain, protects the body from the external environment such as pollution and radiation, sunlight, keeping out harmful microbes and chemicals, and helps to regulate temperature, fluid balance and excretion, involved in endocrine function through the production of Cholecalciferol (D3) by epidermis. Skin care items are pharmaceutical preparations that are meant to be applied to the body's numerous external areas and which exhibit advantageous topical effects and offer defense against deteriorating skin problems. Natural component preparations have been used for millennia for skin care; but, due to consumer concerns about chemical and synthetic compounds, they are now becoming more prevalent in current formulations. Humanity has long used plants as medicines, and before synthetic chemicals with comparable qualities, plants were the primary source of all personal care and cosmetics. Additionally, customer needs, which are highlighted by their growing awareness for purchasing environmentally friendly products, highlight the usage of plant extracts in skin care products. Natural skin care products give the nutrients required for healthy skin, improving skin tone, texture, and appearance. Due to several linked features, including antioxidant capacity, pigmentation inhibition, and antibacterial activity, which can be helpful for attenuating and preventing various skin disorders, herbal extracts are primarily used to skincare formulations. Cosmetics by themselves are insufficient to treat skin issues; they must be combined with natural active substances to undo damage and slow down skin aging. Due to their frequent usage in daily life and avoidance of the adverse effects frequently associated with synthetic goods, herbal skincare and cosmetics have grown significantly in popularity. They are also believed to have efficacy and intrinsic appeal. On the other hand, herbal products have low toxicity and are milder and more biodegradable when compared to synthetic skincare and cosmetic chemicals. In order

to develop newer herbal skincare and cosmetic products with fewer side effects and rich sources of beneficial compounds, numerous studies and researches on medicinal plants are being conducted in various parts of the world. Natural plant molecules remain particularly interesting for these studies and researches. Herbal skincare and cosmetic products have had an exponential rise in popularity over the past few years, both in developed and developing nations. Plant extracts, essential oils, vegetable oils, and bioactive complexes show a huge potential to be used in skincare and cosmetic products to enhance and maintain the physiological and biochemical balance and healthy condition of human skin, given the inherent economic potential in the exploitation of natural resources in ecosystems. The vast majority of synthetic and potentially harmful ingredients used in skincare and cosmetics (health risks associated with phthalates, parabens, petroleum-based chemicals, aluminum salts, etc.) are the primary driving force behind recently developed organic and natural skincare, based on cutting-edge multifunctional formulations that include products with anti-aging, skin-lightening, and super moisturizing benefits.

2.7 DECEPTIVE ADVERTISING

Deceptive advertising, according to Lodhi (2015), is the use of misleading, false, and incorrect marketing of an item that may negatively influence a consumer's loyalty. Duplicity can be confirmed when a buyer exclusively consumes or experiences the good or service. If consumers are not given all the information or are shown images that distort the true qualities of a good or service, they may not be able to make the best decisions for themselves (Ray, 2018). Any business that uses deceptive advertising is no longer one that can be trusted since both new and existing customers may be duped into switching to the goods or services of another business. The company can also develop a bad reputation as a deceitful organization, which would portend

future business decline. In addition, with the constant influx of creative players into potential businesses, it is becoming simpler to determine whether factors like customer happiness, word of mouth, and trust also influence consumer loyalty in developing markets. That is the reason organizations make superior associations with their faithful customers, as they purchase their products and services over and over (Waheed Akhter, 2011). However, this can be done when once trust is developed.

False advertising, as defined by the European Commission, is any advertising that, through any means, including its presentation, is capable of deceiving the person on whom it is focused, misrepresents their behavior, and ultimately harms the interests of the consumers (Official Journal of the European Union, 2005). Misleading advertising is prohibited everywhere, from China to India to the UK. Not only is deception prohibited, but it is also strictly monitored. Advertorials that are available as editorial content must be clearly designated as advertisements in most countries. Breaking these regulations can have severe financial and humanitarian repercussions (Wakeman 2018).

Heyman (2016), there are four things that constitute an advertisement dishonest, according to the Federal Trade Commission (FTC). The standard for "reasonable consumers" is: According to "reasonable customers' point of view who is an average sophisticated and educated looks at the advert rather than focusing on certain terms, the ad is deceptive or not," But the FTC seeks to understand what a customer is being told by every part of an advertisement.

Express vs. implied claims: Another aspect to consider when deciding whether an advertisement is deceptive or not are the explicit and implicit statements it makes. While **express**

claims are made in the advertisement in full, **implied claims** are those that are made subtly or by inference.

Misleading by Omission: If anything crucial misleads consumers and the advertisement omitted to reveal it, authorities may also decide what the advertisement does not say.

Materiality: If the advertisement is misleading or not, it is crucial to establish whether the claim or omission in question is "material"—that is, connected to the consumer's choice to purchase or use the product. Product efficacy, pricing, safety, features, and performance are all mentioned and connected to the substantive claims. Three primary orientations in deceptive advertising have been demonstrated by the researchers in an essay on ethical concerns and customers' rights. The approach used by marketers to embed the advertisement in customers' minds comes in second, followed by the method used to track each person's unique online experience in order to promote businesses' goods (Maleki & Pasha, 2012). According to a study on the requirements and difficulties of unethical advertising, social networking websites on the internet are the newest trend even though billboards, radio, TV, and newspapers are some of the media used to get consumers' attention. Children, teenagers, adults, and the elderly are all exposed to inappropriate advertising, which is a serious concern. And when compared to Malaysia's past and present, this offensive advertising can influence the next generation's damaging beliefs (Bin Nooh et al., 2014).

Most consumers discover the products through marketing. The purchase patterns of customers can be strongly impacted by and changed by advertising. Marketers take advantage of this opportunity and use deceit to entice customers to buy questionable goods.

Advertising might result in consumers misinterpreting advertisement claims, Komal Nagar (2017). People may believe a given assertion they derive from an advertisement, but that does not indicate they were intentionally deceived (Armstrong and Russ, 1975; Grunert and Dedler, 1985). The consumer is not duped by the advertisement if he recognizes the claim as incorrect and does not believe it to be real (Komal Nagar, 2017). Unlike a real claim which can cause significant harm if it inspires incorrect beliefs, a false claim does not hurt consumers unless they believe it (Russo, Metcalf, and Stephens 1981). Additionally, research that examined how ethical standards affected consumer behavior (Hiller, 2010; Roberts, 1995; Shaw and Shiu, 2003; Valor, 2007) discovered that consumers' perceptions of ethics might be influenced by the specifications of the product as well as their own personal value systems (Hiller, 2010).

Gardner (2019) also claims that deception is a behavior that takes place when an advertisement gives the consumer a different impression or belief than what they would typically anticipate given their level of information. Additionally, if this perception or notion is inaccurate or perhaps deceptive, deceit is present. As a defense, Carrigan and Attalla (2001) pointed out that consumers frequently lack the knowledge necessary to determine whether a company's actions are deceptive or not.

2.7.1 TYPES AND TACTICS OF DECEPTIVE ADVERTISEMENT

Chaouachi and Rached (2012) highlighted two major ways of deception in an advertising process; these are – ‘Explicit Deception’ and ‘Implicit Deception’. In explicit deception, the content of the advertisement expressly contains false information. This is the reason for the name ‘explicit’; it explicitly inputs the deceptive information, so much that the deception can be observed when

juxtaposing the actual feature (both physical and functional) of the product, and the message content put out. On the other hand, implicit deception happens when advertisers form their advertised content from factual information that is proven correct, but misleads the consumer by causing them to draw conclusions about the product being advertised. Implicit deceptions have to do with psychological manipulation, through theories adopted from psychology infused with legal frameworks. Implicit deception may not be deciphered immediately, as consumers may find it hard to detect; to detect implicit deception, there must be a comparison between what the consumers have implied from the advertised content, and the original features of the product or service.

Nagody, Ochoa, Chęcinska, and Budziński (2019) show several different popular manipulation techniques inputted in the advertising process message. A major technique is fragmentation; this is where an advertising message portrays convenient parts of the product or service, or the advertiser intentionally puts out just the promotional information that will attract the audience attention, and possibly persuade them to taking purchase decision. In this technique, advertisers intentionally omit issues or unattractive features of the product, and only display features that the consumers want to see. Among the different manipulation techniques, the use of varieties of valuation words, and convincing flattery are the most common (Baryshnikova, 2017). The advertiser manipulates the audience, by convincing them that the product would fulfil the desires and wants that are unique to them. Another popular technique, is the message manipulation technique, which is mostly adopted in television and radio commercials. They are most often found in commercials where the advertisers attempt to convince the audience by adopting wordings, and sometimes, people, to create a certain level trust or confidence. This technique

brings in the false authority of the pseudoscientific professionals and specialists, by hiring actors to play the role.

However, some advertising scholars express their views on deceptive advertising as having some pros and cons (Nagody, Ochoa, Chęcinska, & Budziński, 2019, Fayyaz & Amreen, 2015, Aurélie & Noémie, 2013 et al).

PROS

Techniques are adopted by advertisers because it proposes to create somewhat of a positive effect on the business. Deception adopted as an advertising technique, also has advantages for the advertisers, as other techniques that advertisers use to persuade the consumers. This could be long-term or short-term benefits (Nagody, Ochoa, Chęcinska, & Budziński, 2019).

Deceptive advertising is used by many companies to gain competitive advantage in the market, through its untruthful, enticing, information that leads to brand distinction; a concept to differentiate themselves from competitors. This is why these advertisers and companies put out elaborate and exaggerated information about their product or service (Fayyaz & Amreen, 2015).

This is especially in a market where various companies offer the same or similar products with equal performance, so they resort to deceptive advertising, in order to carve out for themselves – a distinct brand image that leads to market differentiation. It gives them the upper hand with increased demand and purchases, that are as a result of the competitive advantage gotten from

deception. There are outcomes even though businesses who use deceptive advertising are more concerned with their market share and profit than with their customers (Aurélié & Noémie, 2013).

CONS

Deceptive advertising has become a disadvantage to companies that adopt these types of unethical adverts on a long-term basis. It majorly reduces purchase and general customer loyalty. The perceptions of consumers are important for the running of a business; it determines the patronization of the consumers towards the company. For consumers that are deceived, it is imperative that they have a negative perception towards the company, and that leads to a decrease in patronage, purchase, and repurchase of the consumers (Ullah & Hussain, 2015). An/ end result of deceptive advertising, is a break in company- consumer relationship that would ultimately reflect in their market performance.

Another reason why deceptive advertising is not a beneficial element for the company, is the issue of mistrust (Verigin, Meijer, & Vrij, 2019). It should be in the plan of a company to build the trust of its targeted audience. The reputation that a company has affects whether or not the consumers are liable to trust, and this applies vice versa; when consumers trust the company, it builds their reputation. The number of consumers is impacted by the reduction in the number of individuals who will ever trust the product again when customers are tricked, defrauded, or fooled since word of mouth spreads quickly. Low consumer repurchase rates therefore translate into low sales.

This strategy may eliminate all or a portion of future business chances with clients, distributors, and other companies one might partner with for joint advertising and marketing campaigns. Even a company's online presence has an impact on its reputation, which is valuable to an organization.

Any business that uses deceptive advertising is seen as being unreliable, and both new and existing clients may suffer by falling prey to fraud, forcing them to switch to another company's goods or services. Additionally, the company might receive a poor standing and damaged reputation in the eyes of its stakeholders, including investors, shareholders, customers, and potential customers, which would ultimately lead to diminishing economic activity in the future (Ahmed & Saira, 2019).

Ullah and Hussain (2015) explain that deceptive advertising and adverts adopting any form of manipulative and misleading means, generally affects customer purchasing behaviour, due to the fact that when these products are found to be of lesser standard than expected, it negatively affects customer satisfaction; which often times, decreases word-of-mouth customer advertising.

2.8 ANALYSIS OF DECEPTIVE ADVERTISING IN THE SKINCARE AND COSMETIC INDUSTRY

According to Ukaegbu (2020), the skincare sector may be a major contributor to misleading advertising messages. There are questions over whether the flawless-looking beauty queens who appear in the advertisements utilize the skincare products on their skin every day or if it's just a ruse to get the public to buy them. Our traders and producers, from small-scale traders and producers to big-time dealers and producers, all require a thorough mass orientation and reorientation because they display a lot of selfish marketing qualities and attitudes. Every product or service has a benefit or drawback of its own, but they also highlight the benefits and downplay the drawbacks of the product. They therefore require a comprehensive reformation of their moral values and attitudes toward life. It is a significant issue and a roadblock to the economic development of our country because it also harms our reputation abroad.

The situation has gotten so bad that even regulatory organizations like the Standard Organizations of Nigeria (SON), the Advertising Practitioners' Council of Nigeria (APCON), and the Consumer Protection Council resemble toothless bulldogs as consumers are left at the mercy of the deceptive marketing practices of producers, ad media outlets, and traders in our markets. One is left wondering about the duties of the key regulating agencies in advertising in light of these unregulated unethical marketing practices that are destroying the country's moral commercial value system (Ukaegbu, 2020).

Due to the need for consumers to be cautious when making purchases, the phrase "Caveat Emptor" is practically becoming the norm. The long-term effects of these evil deeds, however, boil down to post-purchase dissonance of the product, a lack of repeat business, and low sales, which cause the product to fail in the market and subsequently waste a tremendous amount of the money, time, and other material resources used to produce it. Closing such productive businesses and laying off large numbers of employees will have an overall negative impact on the country and may lead to social vices because laid-off employees must maintain both their physical and mental well-being.

Due to the complexity of the advertising industry, business owners frequently seek professional assistance. This is an especially clever strategy in fields like skin care, where many products are made with women in mind. In addition, ladies buy a lot of male skincare products. More than just promoting the particular goods is involved in advertising skin care products for ladies. The needs of the ideal consumer must be identified for a product to be successful in the market. These days, skin care advertising strategies and themes are far more comprehensive and nuanced. An expert consultant with experience creating skin care marketing strategies would be a priceless asset that can help a brand in various crucial areas.

Understanding the distinctive advantages of each product is necessary for sales success in the skin care industry. Marketers gain knowledge they may utilize in skin care marketing campaigns by studying the advantages each product in their range has for women and how it varies from the competition. Marketers should pay close attention to every element, including how the product feels when applied and its key selling points. Finding the target market for each skin care product is made simpler by becoming familiar with the product line.

2.9 SKINCARE PRODUCTS

According to Muhamad, Ahansul, Kalthom, Zohurul, and Fasai (2019), the majority of people in the world, particularly women, place a high value on appearance. Women are particularly concerned of their faces for a variety of reasons, including exercise, makeup, dressing up, and many other influencing variables. Numerous goods and services are developed to capitalize on this inherent female urge for just this reason. Understanding how women think and behave is necessary for marketing a product that women will inevitably want. Therefore, research on how to advertise a certain product must consider the psychological and social factors that would inherently lure and pull customers' intense interest in the products or services. Today, big personalities that naturally draw large audiences produce successful media advertising that is skillfully scripted, attractively packaged, and delivered in order to pique the target audience's interest. It has been observed that advertisements for skin care products frequently include gorgeous models or well-known individuals. Photos or movies are expertly produced and displayed. If it's a television advertisement, the narration is done in the most provocative and alluring oration to pique the interest of the potential customers. Captions added to them are carefully worded lines to awe and inspire the potential customers. The attractive images that the models who represent or sell such skincare products present are used to bolster claims made

about the numerous advantages or benefits of utilizing such products. Supporting documentation or official confirmation is provided in addition to the information to increase value and credibility. If women can be persuaded that using a certain product will make them look more appealing, it is not difficult to influence their psychology. They will be persuaded regardless of the expense or even any potential hidden problems that may be linked with it.

Skincare products have grown in popularity over time, and an increase in their use can be ascribed to an increase in their online ads, particularly on social media. Due to their well-known affiliation with these products, prominent societal figures, influencers, and celebrities helped to publicize the product (Cleland, Koss, & Muoio, 2002).

2.10 HISTORY OF COSMETIC SKINCARE ADVERTISING

Since the commencement of women's magazines like *Vogue*, cosmetic advertisements have been a part of their content. The history of cosmetic and skincare advertising dates back at least a century (of course, its use is far longer than that) (Jones 2010). The advent of L'Oréal, Elizabeth Arden, and Helena Rubinstein at the beginning of the 20th century marked the beginning of the familiar beauty business and advertising. Following World War One, cosmetics became more affordable and were heavily promoted. Cosmetic advertising has steadily increased since that point. A quick glance through *Vogue* from 1930 reveals that both Helena Rubinstein and Elizabeth Arden are already well-known advertisements. Elizabeth Arden was one of the first in the 20th century to suggest that using cosmetics may make the person look younger. One instance is their 1936 advertisement, which effectively inverts the famous Browning poem from the 19th century and declares, "Farewell to Age! Grow young with me, since the best is yet to come!" (Elizabeth Arden, 1936; Dade, 2007) In one of their 1950 cosmetic adverts, Helena

Rubinstein cited scientific data. This advertisement, which used wording and a tone reminiscent of 21st-century marketing, claimed that regular application of the Contour Lift Film would address sagging contours. Although there were still some advertising addressed at older women who wanted to seem younger, the language, visual imagery, and claims of 1960s advertisements emphasized cosmetic use for younger women and for decorating. In the 1970s, emphasis was placed on products that were "natural," both in terms of appearance and ingredients (Dade 2007). During the last decades of the 20th century, advertising became increasingly targeted at the baby boomer generation, a sizeable but aging demographic. Therefore, it is clear that cosmetics advertising both reflect and represent the cultural eras from which they are produced.

Because there are so many options available to users of skincare products, advertising is crucial. In general, advertisements have been shown to help customers make decisions. Because some advertising delivers inaccurate or misleading information in an effort to influence consumers' purchasing decisions, skincare advertisements have come to be associated with dishonesty (Eisenberg, John, & Rosemary, 2013).

The growing advertising strategy used by the cosmetics business is to blame for the increase in popularity of these products. Through the numerous commercials that have been broadcast on several media, including newspapers, magazines, billboards, supermarket tabloids, roll-up banners, and most notably the internet, consumers have been promised attractiveness through the sold products.

OTC weight-loss products use a variety of various sorts of advertising claims and strategies, as demonstrated by Cleland, Koss, and Muoio (2002), who also identify commonalities in the claims.

2.11.1 CONSUMER TESTIMONIALS

These are among the most widely used methods for convincing people to buy a product by demonstrating the benefits and results of using it. The effectiveness of the product is demonstrated in the skincare advertising that employ this strategy, as is the product's ability to assuage the doubts of potential clients. Advertisers frequently have to persuade customers who, because of bad past experiences, doubt the product's efficacy. Because of this, the purpose of these reviews is to demonstrate that other customers have tried the product and trusted it. This can take a variety of forms.

2.11.2 BEFORE-AND-AFTER PHOTO CLAIMS

These are yet another category of client feedback. It is the presentation of results through offering proof of a visual transformation. Images and videos of actual people using the skincare product could be used as examples of this. The promises are more than simply images and videos to the advertisers since they persuade customers by displaying these before-and-after photos, which give them an idea of what is possible when the product is used (Federal Trade Commission, 2003).

2.12 PRACTICE OF DECEPTIVE ADVERTISING IN SKINCARE PRODUCTS

The majority of people learn about products from commercials. Advertising has the power to significantly affect and change the purchasing habits of consumers. Therefore, marketers take advantage of this situation and utilize deceit to persuade customers to purchase dubious goods. Most of the time, consumers know very little or nothing about a product. Through this false advertising, they may quickly and easily disseminate their false words to their intended audience.

In skin care product arena, advertising is most of them “materialistic”. Different skin care product advertisements are taken for analysis. It is difficult to prove or determining whether these televisions commercials misleading or deceptive. These advertisements are analyzed based on FTC (Federal Trade Commission) concept.

Marketers use false advertising for their own gain and do not consider the outcomes in the long run. But the effects of these misleading marketing on our society and health are significant (Sing & Sandhu 2011). The commercials are moving in a direction that has huge social tension and to which solutions are still not found. The commercials are transferring power to the businesses that have consistently ignored social implications of their actions. (Sujata and Bhawna 2012) have shown that television commercials are playing a vital role to influence the buyers specially the teenagers and young. They are so greatly persuaded by these advertisements that they think they will provide them the same prestige, fulfillment, and happiness. Dandruff, skin rashes, hair loss, and deceptive advertising are just a few of the side effects that can have serious repercussions; therefore the government needs to take appropriate steps to protect consumer rights.

Liepinyte and Daugeliene (2012) demonstrated the relationship between misleading advertising and consumer-friendly solutions as part of Lithuania's institutional framework and regulatory framework. In a qualitative research in Europe, researchers found that purchasing decision of consumer's is ended up through deceptive practices in advertisements at high prices and low quality. For this reason, they have emphasized on fair and decent advertisements. Following the study, the European Union enacted laws and regulations to safeguard consumers from deceptive advertising. In addition, they made sure that customers received the necessary training and knowledge (Monika & Rasa 2012). Advertising that is misleading is a serious problem. Although

it may be a lucrative strategy for marketers, customers are very alarmed by the effects of false marketing.

Langley, (2018) further said that deceptive advertising has affected legitimate businesses by lowering sales and consumer trust in general. A market's success depends on consumer confidence, and as the prevalence of deceptive advertising rises, the number of repeat customers falls. The longer this breach in the consumer/business relationship can go unnoticed, the bigger the market. In extremely small print, "disclosure" statements are typically included in car sales, finance payment plans, and service agreements to explain any additional fees or restrictions that are not immediately obvious while purchasing the good or service. Consumers are ultimately accountable for making informed decisions when making purchases of goods and services, even with the government's monitoring. Trust is the main factor that deceitful advertising undermines for businesses (Goessl, 2010). To flourish, a company needs to win the trust of its customers to some extent. We are all aware that negative news spreads faster than positive news. Without a doubt, cheating will reduce the amount of people who will ever again have faith in that individual. Future business opportunities with clients, distributors, and other businesses you might collaborate with on joint marketing and advertising campaigns would be gone. Even in the online world where no one can see your face, your reputation is still valuable. It still has significance. (Wilson, 2010).

2.13 CONSUMER'S SUSCEPTIBILITY AND PERCEPTION TO DECEPTIVE ADVERTISING

The degree to which people pay attention to and appreciate commercial messages as sources of information for influencing their consumption behavior is referred to as the consumer's

susceptibility to advertising (Barr & Kellaris, 2015). Susceptibility encompasses the circumstances under which consumers may or cannot recognize false claims, the psychological mechanisms of being duped, and the impact of regulatory measures (Armstrong, Gurol, and Russ, 1979). (Darke & Ritchie, 2007). According to research, false statements, situational settings, and consumer traits interact to cause high vulnerability (Xie & Boush, 2016).

Advertising claims, according to Kotler and Armstrong (2010), are the spoken signals that communicate important information about a product's or service's features. When it comes to misleading advertising, the statements are made with the objective to mislead consumers into reading beyond the literal message and coming to the wrong conclusions about the promoted good or service (Hastak & Mazis, 2011). Despite the abundance of fraudulent promises, a critical concern is whether customers can recognize them (Vladeck, 2000). Consumers are more prone to be duped when they rely on advertisements for information and trust claims (Oslon & Dover, 1978). When consumers possess diagnostic or product expertise, are aware of misleading tactics, or have had product and service experience, they may be less susceptible to deceptive advertising (Barone, Palan and Miniard, 2016). Deceptive claims, however, make use of numerous assumptions without defining the precise and appropriate meanings in certain settings (Xie & Boush, 2016). Additionally, many false claims in today's world are impliedly manipulative as opposed to being wholly untrue (Mazis, 2011).

Consumers may either perform worse or better when they are aware of deceptive advertising and how it works, according to Xie and Boush (2016), depending on their current emotional or cognitive states, which affect how they process information, and the immediate environment in which the claim is made. Situational contexts refer to this collection of variables. Detection and attention can be difficult cognitive tasks in the context of deceptive advertising that call for

particular sorts and levels of drive and aptitude. Customers aren't always extremely motivated or adept at spotting false advertising. They may be more vulnerable if they are preoccupied when exposed to the ads (Xie and Boush, 2016).

Celsi and Olson (2018) assert, however, that susceptibility can vary depending on how consumers interpret claims, including processing participation, inferential techniques, and information relevance. Additionally, a consumer's motivational and emotional state affects their style and focus, making it harder for them to recognize false claims.

According to Darke and Ritchie (2017), customers can become protective once they become aware that there is a chance they could be duped. Then, we see unfavorable reactions like mistrust. As a precaution, these responses lessen the likelihood of being tricked. These responses might be quick enough and strong enough to negate the reason for examining the alternatives that accuracy offers. As a result, criticism is directed not only at dishonest advertising but also at others, even when they are not dishonest (Ashworth & Main, 2010).

When consumers notice fraudulent advertising promises, they react to them differently; studies have explored these responses using consumers' dispositional and developmental traits. Dispositional differences are traits that alter depending on factors including age, family, gender, and way of life (Janet, 1985). According to Mir (2011), the amount of effort consumers must expend to recollect knowledge-based elements when processing information from a particular advertisement depends on their age. Differences based on a consumer's knowledge and skill development through time are referred to as developmental differences.

Consumer knowledge progresses from the perceptual stage through the logical stage, and finally to the reflective level, according to Hosseini et al. (2016). The degree to which a consumer is

vulnerable to deceptive advertising changes as they grow from children to adults. focusing on transient business cognitive aspects (Hackley, 2010, Soroa-Koury & Yang, 2010). Depending on their expertise and motivation, consumers can tell the difference between genuine and false advertising. Additionally, when consumers are not aware of deceptive promises, they are more vulnerable to fraudulent advertising. Consumers' propensity to base decisions on deceptive advertising is believed to depend on situational situations and individual traits (Hackley, 2010; Faerber & Kreling, 2014).

Perception is crucial to the advertising process because it reveals how consumers perceive a company's good or service, and it is one of the most significant elements influencing consumer purchasing behavior (Azeem & Haq, 2012). Most frequently, marketers employ well-considered and clever strategies to try to change the target audience's perception of the product or service. Utilizing knowledge and research on how consumers view their product or service, advertising can create persuasive material that is tailored to those audiences. In order to make sure that the promoted item is remembered and remembered favorably, they could also make strategic adjustments and improvements. Advertisers must be familiar with sensory thresholds, perception, and how consumers create their perceptions. With this knowledge, advertisers may now modify marketing stimuli like advertisements, packaging, and pricing.

2.14 UNDERSTANDING CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR AND PURCHASE

DECISION PROCESS

Consumer behavior refers to the purchasing habits of ultimate consumers—individuals and households—who purchase products and services for their own use, according to Kotler and Armstrong (2010). Consumer buying behavior, according to Solomon (2009), is the study of the

steps taken by people or groups when they choose, buy, utilize, or discard goods, services, concepts, or experiences in order to satiate their needs and desires.

According to Mansoor and Jalal (2011), consumer purchasing behavior can take many different shapes and depend on a wide range of variables, including income, demography, social issues, and cultural factors.

Consumer decision is eventually influenced by advertising, whether it be through outdoor advertising or any other type of advertising. An effective advertisement is one that persuades viewers to purchase a product based on details offered by the seller. Before and after the purchase, a complicated series of activities covering many points make up the buying behavior process (Hansen, Percy, & Hansen, 2004). The buying decision process comprises five stages: identifying the need, gathering information, weighing the options, making the choice to buy, and following up with actions (Comegys and Hannula, 2006). Long before the actual purchase, the purchasing process begins and lasts. Instead than only focusing on the purchase decision, marketers must address the complete purchasing process (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010).

a) **Need or Problem recognition:** is the first step in the purchasing process where the buyer recognizes a need or a problem. According to Solomon (2009), the consumer will recognize a problem whenever there is a noticeable contrast between his or her actual situation and a desired or ideal state. Both internal and external cues, such as hunger, thirst, sex, education, or psychological concerns, might cause the need to arise (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010).

b) **Information Research:** the point at which a customer becomes interested enough to look for more details about a good or service (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010). Information can be found by the consumer from a variety of sources. Kotler and Armstrong (2010) state that some of these

sources are commercial—such as advertisements, packaging, displays, or salespeople—personal—such as friends, family, or acquaintances, public—such as Internet research or mass media, and experiential—such as handling, examining, or using the product. The extent of the information search is determined by the consumer's prior knowledge and the perceived risk of the transaction. The amount of information research is anticipated to be reduced if there is prior, in-depth understanding about the product (Comegys & Hannula, 2006).

c) **Evaluation of alternatives:** is the stage where the client uses the evidence to evaluate competing brands in the choice set. These analyses employ no specific technique. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2010), the method that customers use to assess their purchase options depends on the individual consumer and the particular buying circumstance.

d) **Purchase decision:** includes all the choices that were ranked in the previous stage. Because it is the choice they value most, the consumer will pick the first one. However, there are two things that could alter consumers' perceptions: other people's perspectives and certain unforeseen situational situations (Comegys and Hannula, 2006).

e) **Post-purchase behaviour:** is the stage that affects businesses more than consumers. If businesses want consumer loyalty, they must look out for their needs. Most of the time, customer loyalty results from customer satisfaction (Comegys and Hannula, 2006). Some purchasing, such as impulsive buying, does not adhere to this process claim, Comegys and Hannula (2006). Consumers do not adhere to any method; instead, they are primarily motivated by their own feelings.

2.15 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.15.1 PERCEPTION THEORY

The audience's perception of the media content that is intended for them is explained by the perception theory. The process of communication is greatly influenced by perception. The selective process is highlighted by the perception theory and can be represented by four rings of defenses of selective exposure, attention, and retention (Dhaliwal, 2016).

The idea of selective perception demonstrates how desires, needs, attitudes, and other psychological factors decide and affect perception. People often decode communication messages using their needs, wants, past experiences, moods, values, and memories rather than just the message's meaning, which indicates that there is a tendency for perception to be defined, formed, and influenced by a variety of different external and internal factors. Different people respond differently to the same message (Christy, 2015). Three processes that are connected to communication have characteristics with selective perception. These are; Selective exposure, selective attention, and selective retention

Selective Exposure: This describes why people look for contents and information that suits their individual interests and worldviews. People naturally steer clear of opposing ideas and viewpoints that criticize their values and public persona. Selective exposure is the propensity for people to be exposed to communications that support their current attitude while avoiding those that do not.

Selective Attention: In order to avoid confusion, the human brain must choose which information to focus on at any particular time. Selective attention is the propensity for people to pay attention to parts of a message that are consistent with firmly held attitudes, views, or behaviors, while ignoring parts of a message that are inconsistent with similar attitudes, beliefs, or behaviors.

Selective Retention: This is the propensity for desires, needs, attitudes, and other psychological factors to have an impact on memory. We remember the message and, more precisely, we remember positive messages. Retention rates are also known to be influenced by the saliency of the message (relevance to our needs), the mode of delivery, and the receiver's interests and beliefs. This theory clarifies the problem of customer attention, retention, and perception and demonstrates how various individuals respond to the same message in various ways. The audience interprets messages in various ways, thus it is important to take these interpretations into account and compare them when examining how advertising messages are perceived.

2.16 IMPLICATION OF THE THEORY

Advertisements of skincare products are interpreted in different ways. Consumers may pay more attention to these adverts because of their prior knowledge, belief and values; they retain the information on these adverts because of the same reasons. This therefore affects how they perceive the advertisements, and further determines how they select the advert to be persuaded by. This theory applies to women whose perceptions are affected by their wants, needs, attitudes and other psychological factors; deceptive advertisements that may play on their want for a 'better body', affects the perception of the women. The goal of the study is to find out the perception of Covenant University female students towards Jenny's glow skincare product

deceptive advertisement. This is why their beliefs, knowledge, values, language, culture and other factors, need understand the interpretation of the message fully. Daily information is offered to women, and advertising serves as a source of information for the audience. Because of this, presentation is a key responsibility of the advertiser, but the decision-making ultimately rests with the consumer.

2.17 REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Fayyaz and Amreen (2015) examine deceptive advertising on mobile phones, and its influence on customers' loyalty. Their study analyses mobile phone advertisements, and the deceptive elements in mobile phone advertisements, as it relates to the effect that it has on customers' loyalty. The study concluded that customers are not happy with the advertisements that they perceive to be deceptive, and as a result, their trust in the phone brand starts depleting – because their experience of the phone in comparison to what was advertised, is inconsistent. The study examined that not only does the deceptive advert reduce their loyalty, but it causes them to dissuade others from purchasing the product. When this happens, it is almost impossible that the producer would enjoy a good market share.

Similarly, Ahmed and Saira (2019) study the deception in the telecommunication advertisements, and seeks to find out how it affects the customers' loyalty. The study shows that the loyalty of customers is negatively affected by the deception of the advertisements; although, the patronage of the telecommunication industry is almost a necessity, the customers' choice of where their brand loyalty lies, dwindles.

Hayder (2017) studies skin-care deceptive advertising in relations to buying behaviors of university students. The research gathers information on deception and its impact on skin-care

purchase. The displayed results showed that deceptive adverts led to an increase in the purchase of skincare products. Unlike previous studies that produced a negative result, this study recorded a significantly positive impact to skin care usage and purchases.

A research of skincare products in Malaysia by Muhammad Tahir Jan et al. (2019) explores the components of advertising and their effects on consumer behavior. The primary goal of the study is to determine how important advertising aspects affect consumers' decisions to purchase skincare products. This study sets out to examine how a different aspect of advertising affects consumers' purchasing decisions. The study found that two aspects of advertising—their utility and their features—have a considerable beneficial influence on consumers' purchasing decisions.

A study on skin-care products in Bangladesh by Nashid Bintey Hayder (2017) examines the deceptive advertising and shopping habits of university students. This study tries to identify the misleading advertising that various skin care products in Bangladesh provide. The study demonstrates that deceptive advertising has the greatest influence on customer purchasing decisions.

Using the example of over-the-counter weight loss products, John Cawley et al. (2013) investigates the impact of deceptive advertising on the consumption of the marketed good and its alternatives. This study investigates how exposure to misleading advertising affects consumer consumption of the advertised product and its alternatives.

Nafisa Newaz (2017) investigates how misleading advertising affects female consumers. Consumers are exposed to hundreds of marketing messages, according to the report. It primarily seeks to understand how misleading advertising affects female consumers. It also aims at identifying the social and health effects of deceptive advertising on female customers.

Modi Vishakhaben and Pankaj Sharma (2021) investigate Indian consumers' perceptions and responses to misleading hair care product marketing. The study investigates the elements influencing how consumers perceive the credibility of adverts with a focus on how consumers perceive and respond to misleading commercials. This study explains how consumers respond to misleading hair care product marketing. Additionally, it describes the connection between client demographics & responses to deceptive advertising. The study also benefits companies, marketers, academics, and researchers.

An empirical study on university students in Libya by Hazem Rasheed Gaber et al. (2018) examines the impact of marketing deception on consumer purchasing decisions on Facebook. This study examines how marketing deception affects consumer behavior. It specifically looks into the impact of misleading techniques on the customer purchasing process in relation to the product, price, place, and promotion.

In the example of Pakistan, Najeeb Ullah et al. (2015) investigates the effects of unethical advertising, false information, or deceptive advertising on consumer purchasing intentions. The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of unethical advertising, false information or deception, and stereotype advertising on consumer purchase intentions. The study demonstrates the negative correlation between unethical advertising, false information, and stereotypical advertising and consumer purchasing behavior or intention, as well as the negative correlation between word-of-mouth and consumer pleasure.

2.18 GAPS TO FILL

This work aims to examine Jenny's Glow skincare product deceptive advertisement and studies the perception of Covenant University female students on these advertisements. While past

works have looked at skincare advertising, there are little to no studies on the perception of Covenant University female students towards these advertisements in Nigeria. This work aims to bridge that gap. Also, this work aims to analyse in Nigeria; examining these adverts for deceptive elements, and understanding the audience knowledge on deceptive skincare product advertisement.

The gaps in the review of empirical studies that this research provides is the fact that this study is on Covenant University female students and there is no study under the empirical review that focuses on that. There is also no study under the empirical review that focuses on Jenny's Glow skincare product. The solution to this is that more researches should be done on other private schools and states too and also on male respondents as this research focuses only on female respondents.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter includes the methodological approaches and procedures to be used in this study. This includes the research design, population of the study, sample size, description of research instrument, validity of research instrument, reliability of research instrument, method of data collection and method of data analysis.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

The method adopted for this study is the survey design. The research therefore used the survey design because of its cross-sectional approach that involves seeking views of Covenant University female students on deceptive advertising and their perception on Jenny's glow adverts.

3.2 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population for the survey includes Covenant University female students totaling 3,699 (Covenant University) that have used Jenny's glow skincare product and have watched their adverts on their social media platform. Aliza, Malik, Ali, & Muhammad (2019) study that marketing of skincare products is mainly targeted at vulnerable younger and aged women.

3.3 SAMPLE SIZE

The choice of the Taro Yamane approach is because the population is finite and known (N is the summation of all Covenant University female students).

3.4 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

For the survey, the researcher used both purposive sampling and quota sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique was used because the research was aimed at Covenant University female students that have heard of, seen and used Jenny's Glow skincare product. Quota sampling technique was used because the researcher selected equally from all the faculties making the study population.

3.5 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF INSTRUMENT

The data collection instruments were verified and approved by departmental lecturers to ensure that the researcher gets adequate and necessary information from respondents. Before it was used for data collection, the questionnaire was vetted thoroughly. The questionnaire was pre-tested in a pilot study to avoid omissions or errors in the instruments. Twenty copies were distributed to ensure the reliability of the questionnaire.

3.6 METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Copies from the questionnaire will be distributed by the researcher, there will be no need for a research assistant as the questions will be self-administered. This is to make it easy for the respondents to easily access the researcher and ask questions that regard to filling out the form.

The questionnaire will be limited to one copy per individual and each respondent is advised to answer honestly.

3.7 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The data derived from the survey were presented and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS), research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency and percentages. The data analyzed were presented in tables and percentages. Data were presented in SPSS format, and the analyzed and presented data, determined the final answer to all five research questions which this paper sought to find answers to.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.1 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This section contains presentation of analysis of data in table, and detailed discussion of result was also done.

The data presentation and analysis are to answer the Research Question. In essence, the data analyses are presented responses to each research question. 348 questionnaires were administered and all the 348 questionnaires were filled and returned.

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Value and Percentages (%)					Total
Age	14-20	21-25	26-30	30 and above		
	52.3	34.8	11.5	1.4		100 n=348
College	CMSS	COE	CST	CLDS		
	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0		100 n=348
Sex	Male	Female				
	0	100				100 n=348
Level	100	200	300	400	500	
	25.6	20.7	14.7	15.2	23.9	100 n=348
Religion	Christian	Muslim	Others			
	97.4	2.3	0.3			100 n=348

From the descriptive statistics table above, a total of 348 students participated in the study, and all were female. They were aged from 14 years and above, with the highest age range reported was between 14-20 years which accounted for 52.3% of the participants. Following this were those within the ages of 21-25 as they made up 34.8% of the study participant. Next were those between ages 26-30 which accounted for 11.5%, and only 1.4% of the participants were 30 years and above. The high number of participants from 14 to 25 years were prevalent, as these are the years heavy cosmetic and body toning usage is prevalent.

For the colleges, the participants were equal in their representation. 25% of the participants each were drawn from all the colleges (College of Engineering, College of Management and Social Sciences, College of Science and Technology and College of Leadership and Developmental Studies respectively).

100 level students were the highest participants, as they accounted for 25.6% of the participants, which was closely followed by 500 level students who accounted for 23.9%. a total of 20.7% and 15.2% of the participants were drawn from 200 and 400 level respectively, while the least number was drawn from 300 level, accounting for only 14.7%.

For religion, not surprising, as 97.4% were Christians, looking at the Christian background of the study population; Covenant University, Ota, Ogun State. 2.3% of the participants were Muslim, while only 0.3% reported other religion.

Research Question 1: What is the level of knowledge of Covenant University female students towards deceptive advertisements?

Table 4.2: Respondents' knowledge of deceptive advertising

Values	Percentage (%)
Yes	89.1
No	7.2
Not Sure	3.7
Total	100
	n=348

Deceptive advertising is evident in the society, which has been known by many; hence, from the table, 89.1% of the participant reported that they have heard about deceptive advertising. Naturally, not all may have heard about it, as it may not be of interest to them; hence, 7.2% reported they are yet to hear about deceptive advertising, while only 3.7% were not sure if they have heard about it or not.

Table 4.3: Respondents' exposure to deceptive advertising on platforms

Values	Percentage (%)
Yes	87.4
No	9.5
Not Sure	3.2
Total	100%
	n=348

In similar outcome, almost everyone purchases something, and sometimes, it fails to meet the expectation from what was advertised. In line with this, 87.4% of the participants reported they

have experienced deceptive advertising, 9.5% reported no experience, while 3.2% were not sure of the experience.

Table 4.4: Mediums where respondents came across deceptive advertisements

Values	Percentage (%)
Radio	0.3
Television	5.2
Billboard	4.9
Social Media	80.5
No Medium	9.2
Total	100%
	n=348

For those who have been exposed to deceptive advertising, the highest medium of exposure was social media, as it accounted for 80.5%, which was not surprising, looking at the increase in time spent on social media, the increase in users, and the high level of social media ads to reach large number of people. Following this was television, which accounted for 5.2%, the next was billboard, accounting for 4.9%, while radio only accounted to 0.3%. 9.2% reported they haven't been exposed, with their response on no medium suggesting that.

Table 4.5: Respondents' knowledge of advertisement of skincare products

Values	Percentage (%)
Yes	100

No	0
Total	100%
	n=348

All the participants have heard or seen advertisement on skincare products. This is largely influenced by social media usage, and the automatic ads that pop out even when the user is not interested. Some of them might be skin care ads, especially for ladies, as the ads pop out in line with perceived target who may have interest or need of the product.

Table 4.6: Medium where respondents saw advertisements of skincare products

Values	Percentage (%)
Television	3.2
Billboard	4.0
Social Media	92.8
Total	100%
	n=348

As stated above about medium of advertising, similar result was obtained on the medium of exposure to skincare advertisement. Social media accounted for the highest medium that participants hear or see about skincare products, revealing 92.8% of the participants. This was followed by billboard, which polled 4.0%, and lastly by television which polled 3.2%.

Research Question 2: To what extent has Covenant University students been exposed to Jenny’s Glow advertisement?

Table 4.7: Assessment of Respondents exposure to Jenny’s Glow advert

Values	Responses in Percentage (%)				
	SA	A	U	D	SD
I have seen advertisements of Jenny’s Glow skincare products	50.3	36.2	6.6	4.6	2.3
I am well knowledgeable about the advertisements of Jenny’s Glow skincare products	47.1	37.1	7.5	5.7	2.6
I am very aware of the advertisements of Jenny’s Glow skincare product	46.8	37.9	8.0	4.3	2.9

From the table, majority of the participants reported having been exposed to Jenny’s Glow skincare product advertisement. Breaking it down, 50.3% strongly agreed they have seen advertisement of Jenny’s Glow skincare product, 36.2% agreed to the assertion, 6.6% were undecided on whether they have or have not seen such advertisement, 4.6% disagreed with the assertion, as they were yet to see adverts of Jenny’s Gold skincare products, while 2.3% strongly disagreed. In terms of being knowledgeable about the advertisement of Jenny’s Glow skincare products, similar outcome was observed, with 47.1% standing strongly with the assertion, 37.1% affirmed to the assertion, 7.5% were undecided about it, 5.7% disagreed on the knowledge regarding advertisement of Jenny’s Gold skincare products, while 2.6% strongly disagreed to the assertion. When asked on the awareness of the participants on the awareness of Jenny’s Glow skincare advertisement, majority affirmed being aware of such advertisement. Breaking it down,

46.8% strongly agreed to being aware of the advertisement, 37.9% agreed with the assertion, 8.0% were undecided, 4.3% disagreed on being aware of such type of advert, while 2.9% strongly disagreed on it.

Research Question 3: What is the perception of Covenant University Students on Jenny’s Glow Advertisement?

Table 4.8: Perception of respondents to Jenny’s Glow Adverts

Values	Responses in Percentage (%)				
	SA	A	U	D	SD
Jenny’s Glow advertisements are informative	4.9	9.5	19.0	35.3	31.3
Jenny’s Glow advertisements are factual	5.2	6.0	19.3	36.2	33.3
Jenny’s Glow advertisements are misleading	36.8	28.7	23.0	5.2	6.3
Jenny’s Glow advertisements are offensive	27.9	35.1	23.9	6.0	7.2
Jenny’s Glow models used for Jenny’s Glow advertisements are deceptive	35.6	31.9	22.1	4.3	6.1

Values	Responses in Percentage (%)
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	SA	A	U	D	SD
Jenny's Glow uses models and influencers with already clear skin for their advertisements	29.9	34.5	24.7	4.3	6.6
Adverts that claim that Jenny's Glow will make users have permanent good skin even when they stop usage are correct	2.3	9.2	18.1	36.5	33.9

Regarding the perception of the participants on the contents of Jenny's Glow skincare products advert, few participants reported on the informative aspect of the content, with 4.9% and 9.5% strongly agreeing and agreeing respectively to the assertion, as they believed the contents were informative enough. 19.0% of the participants were undecided as regards that, while more than half of the participants reported that they do not gain anything meaningful from the advert in question, as 35.3% and 31.3% disagreeing and strongly disagreeing on the informative aspect of the advertisement. Similar trend was observed in respect to how factual the contents were. 36.2% of the participants agreed that the contents from Jenny's Glow skincare products adverts weren't factual, 33.3% had a very strong firm as regards that, while 19.3% were undecided on whether it was factual or not. On the flip, 6.0% agreed that the contents from the adverts were factual, while 5.2% strongly agreed to that.

Furthermore, a good number of participants affirmed that Jenny's Glow advertisements were misleading, with 36.8% and 28.7% strongly agreeing and agreeing respectively to the assertion. 23.0% were undecided, which is a good number, while 5.2% and 6.3% reported that Jenny's

Glow adverts were not misleading, as they disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. On the offensive nature of the contents from the adverts, 27.9% strongly agreed that the contents from the adverts were offensive, 35.1% agreed to the assertion, 22.1% were undecided on whether it was offensive or not, 6.0% disagreed with the offensive nature of the advert, while 7.2% strongly disagreed with the offensive nature of the adverts.

When enquiries were made on the deceptive nature of Jenny's Glow skincare products advert models, greater percentage reported that the models used in the adverts were deceptive in nature, while few reported that they were real. Breaking it down, 35.6% strongly agreed to the deceptive nature of the models used in the adverts, 31.9% agreed to it, 22.1% were undecided on whether the models were deceptive or real, 4.3% disagreed with the assertion, as they had the belief that the models were real, while 6.1% strongly disagreed to it. Speaking more on the deceptive nature of the advert models, majority of the participants reported that these models already have good and clear skins before being called to run the adverts; hence, the products were not responsible for their good looking skins, while few said otherwise. In line with this, 29.9% strongly affirmed to the assertion that these models already have clear skin prior to employing them for the adverts, 34.5% agreed with such assertion, 24.7% were undecided on whether the products made them have good skin or they had good skin prior to using the products in adverts, 4.3% said otherwise that they had no good skin prior to using the product; hence, the product contributed to their clear skin, while 6.6% strongly backed this up.

In continuation with the deceptive nature of the adverts, majority of the participants reported that the claim that Jenny's Glow skincare products will leave users with permanent good skin after use is false. Backing this up, 36.5% disagreed with the assertion that the product will leave permanent good skin even after use, as the product has no power to actualize such claim, while

33.9 strongly disagreed with such assertion. 18.1% of the participants were undecided, 9.1% agreed that the product has the tendency to leave permanent good and clear skin even after stopping the usage of the product, while only 2.3% strongly agreed to that.

Research Question 4: What are the consequences of deceptive skincare products adverts on Covenant University female students?

Table 4.9: Purchase of Jenny’s Glow skincare product because of respondent exposure to the advertised product

Values	Percentage (%)
Yes	76.1
No	20.4
Not Sure	3.4
Total	100%
	n=348

Majority of the participants, that is, 76.1% affirmed that they have purchased Jenny’s Glow skincare products because they have been exposed to their adverts, 20.4% reported they were yet to be influenced by the adverts to purchase the product, while 3.4 were not sure about that.

Table 4.10: Respondents usage of Jenny’s Glow skincare product

Values	Percentage (%)
Yes	79.6
No	17.5

Not Sure	2.9
Total	100%
	n=348

In terms of the usage of Jenny’s Glow skincare products, 79.6% reported they have used the products before, 17.5% said otherwise, while 2.9% said they were not sure if they have used the product or not.

Table 4.11: Duration of respondents’ Jenny’s Glow usage

Values	Percentage (%)
Less than 3 months	27.3
6 months	31.0
A year	12.6
More than a year	8.3
I have not used it before	20.7
Total	100 %
	n=348

For those who have used Jenny’s Glow skincare products, 31.0% have used it for 6 months, 27.3% have used it for less than 3 months, 20.7% are yet to use the product, 12.6% have used the product for a year, while 8.3% have used the product for more than a year.

Table 4.12: Reasons why respondents stopped usage of the product

Values	Percentage (%)
It was fake	14.7
It didn't work for me	19.5
I had reactions from it	18.1
It damaged my skin	15.2
I am not using it	21.3
It is working for me	11.2
Total	100%
	n=348

For participants who have been using the product, they reported they stopped using the product due to some reasons. On the top of their reason was that the product didn't work for them, as reported by 19.5% of the participants, 18.1% reported that the product left reactions on their skin, which made them discontinue the product, 15.2% reported they had skin damage as a result of using the product; hence, they discontinued the product use, while 14.7% reported that the product was fake which led them to stop using the product. However, 11.2% of the participants reported that the product was working for them, while 21.3% reported they are yet to make use of the products.

Table 4.13: Respondents' current usage of Jenny's Glow

Values	Percentage (%)
Yes	14.9
No	85.1

Total	100%
	n=348

The report above affected the current usage of the product, while 14.9% reported still making use of the product, 85.1% reported that they are no longer making use of the product.

Table 4.14: Respondents’ duration of current usage of Jenny’s Glow skincare product

Values	Percentage (%)
Less than 3 months	18.4
6 months	25.9
A year	10.6
More than a year	8.3
I am not currently using it	36.8
Total	100%
	n=348

Backing the above in terms of those currently making use of it, and how long they have been using it, 25.9% reported they have been making use of the product for 6 months, 18.4% reported they have been making use of it for less than 3 months, 10.6% reported they have been using it for a year, while only 8.3% reported they have been using it for more than a year. However, 36.8% reported that they are not currently making use of the product.

Table 4.15: Respondents’ awareness that using fake/adulterated skincare product is dangerous

Values	Percentage (%)
Yes	99.4
Not Sure	0.6
Total	100%
	n=348

In terms of the awareness of the dangers posed in using fake skincare products, 99.4% reported they are aware of the dangers associated with using adulterated or fake skincare products, while only 0.6% reported not being aware of the dangers the use of such product may pose to the individual.

Table 4.16: Dangers of using fake/adulterated skincare products

Values	Percentage (%)
Skin reaction	36.2
Hyperpigmentation	8.9
Discolouration	16.4
Skin cancer	23.3
Acne	15.2
Total	100%
	n=348

Participant went down from knowing that usage of adulterated or fake skincare products are dangerous to an individual to reporting some of the dangers such usage might pose. The most prevalent danger as reported by participant was skin reaction, which accounted for 36.2%. this

was closely followed by skin cancer, which accounted for 23.3%. the next danger was discoloration which accounted for 16.4%, and hyperpigmentation which accounted for 8.9%.

Research Question 5: What are the solutions and recommendations that could be proffered to avoid deceptive advertising of Jenny’s Glow?

Table 4.17: Possible solutions to avoid deceptive advertising of skincare products

Values	Percentage (%)
Enactment of Law protecting customer’s rights	49.7
Establishing new advertising codes to control contents of advertising	25.0
Organizing seminars and conferences on deceptive advertising	10.1
Levelling fines on advertising agencies and companies practicing deceptive advertising	15.2
Total	100%
	n=348

As reported by the participants, majority of them; that is, 49.7% stated that enacting laws protecting customers’ rights will serve as a possible solution to avoid deceptive adverts of skincare products. The next possible solution was establishing a new advertising codes to control contents of adverts as vetoed by 25.0% of the participants. Following this was levelling fines on advertising agencies and companies practicing deceptive advertising, as vetoed by 15.2%, while the least possible solution reported by participants was organizing seminars and conferences on deceptive advertising which was vetoed by 10.1%.

Table 4.18: Respondents view of what should be done to the manufacturers of Jenny’s Glow

Values	Percentage (%)
They should be sued	28.2
They should be banned	24.1
Nothing. They are simply advertising	20.7
Their adverts should be checked by regulatory bodies like APCON	21.3
I'm not familiar with the product	5.7
Total	100%
	n=348

In continuation with the possible solution, and their firsthand experiences of deceptive adverts with Jenny's Glow skincare products. Pointing out punishments they should face, 28.2% of the participants vetoed that they should be sued for putting up deceptive adverts, looking at the negative effect of such on the body. While some agreed on legal action, 24.1% vetoed that they should be banned from operation. Surprisingly, 20.7% said nothing should be done to them as they were simply running ads, 21.3% vetoed that their adverts need to be checked by regulatory bodies like APCON, while 5.7% reported that they weren't familiar with the product.

4.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1: What is the level of knowledge of Covenant University female students towards deceptive advertisements?

The findings from this study revealed that they have heard, read or seen deceptive adverts before. In addition to this, aside being knowledgeable about these deceptive adverts, they have had first-hand experiences of deceptive adverts where they have been made to make purchase of products due to the adverts placed, only to discover that the product didn't meet the expectations from the adverts. Most of these exposures they had with deceptive advertisement were through social media use. This is not surprising with the increase in social media usage over the years (Kemp,

2020); hence, the increased number serves as a market for business owners to market their products, as it gave room for different paid ads.

Furthermore, participants who were ladies, all reported to have heard about adverts involving skincare products. Backing this up, Muhamad, Ahansul, Kalthom, Zohurul and Fasai (2019) observed that Looking good is a priority for most people in the world, especially for females; hence, it is not surprising if they have heard about skincare products, as they all want to look good, especially their skins. In addition, skincare products were popularized through the influence of popular societal figures, influencers and celebrities, due to their known association with these products (Cleland, Koss, & Muoio, 2002), and these celebrities serve as models which people follow.

How these participants came about this information were majorly through social media. Social media ads are sorted in respect to the interest of people. Skincare products ads are well channeled to ladies as they are the target market who will make patronage. Aside this, most of the ladies follow these celebrities on social media, and these celebrities advertise these skincare products on their social media platforms.

Research Question 2: To what extent has Covenant University students been exposed to Jenny's Glow advertisement?

Participants have been well exposed to Jenny's Glow advertisement. Most of the skincare companies sell with advertisements, as they require practical to show the efficacy of their products, in order to attract customers. These ads come through social media platforms like Instagram, with celebrities being used as influencers to market the product. Jayesh and Pradif (2014) opined that women are now conscious of how they look; hence, marketers have brought

about various alternatives to change the looks. These alternatives rests on different adverts which they put out, using mediums like billboards, and most prevalent, social media. It now brings about flooding of different skincare products, like Jenny's Glow skincare product to the awareness of ladies, in order to bring about patronage, with the belief most ladies want to be seen to be attractive in respect to the nature of their skins.

Research Question 3: What is the perception of Covenant University Students on Jenny's Glow Advertisement?

The perception of Covenant University students on Jenny's Glow adverts is on the negative side. Perception naturally comes from interaction between an individual with the perceived object. Zia (2016) explains that advertisers communicate information that is aimed at informing and persuading the audience about a product or service, and its means of production. In line with this, the adverts of Jenny's Glow skincare product have brought about patronage which led to the negative perception. The participants in rating the product reported that the adverts were not factual, were misleading, were not informative, were deceptive and were offensive. An aspect of the perception which drew attention was that of the models Jenny's Glow skincare products used for their adverts. They reported that these models were not truthful, as they already had clear skins before putting up the advert; hence, it was misleading to believe that the product led to their clear skins. In addition, these models reported that the product will leave a permanent clear skin even after stopping the usage of the product, which these participants reported as deceptive. Not surprising with this report as Ukaegbu (2020) explains that the skincare industry may be one of the key leaders in deceptive advertisement messages.

This deceptive advertising can bring destructive thoughts to the next generation compared from the past and the present in Malaysia (Bin Nooh et al., 2014). This is backed up as when one is deceived to purchase a product, it has a tendency of influencing their subsequent purchase of the product, which may be passed down to generations. Expanding on this, Langley, (2018) further added that deceptive advertising has hurt the legitimate business by reducing patronage and the overall confidence in products. Backing the negative perception of deceptive advertising in literature, Ahmed and Saira (2019) affected customers' loyalty due to their perception of the said adverts.

Research Question 4: What are the consequences of deceptive skincare products adverts on Covenant University female students?

The consequences of a product are in relation to how ineffective the product is to populace. Participants responded that most skincare products, like the Jenny's Glow skincare product are fake, Generally, deceptive advertisements have serious impact on our health and society (Sing & Sandhu 2011). Some of the effect of these skincare products are in respect to skin damage and reaction. Participants reported that deceptive skincare products lead to skin reaction, hyperpigmentation, discoloration, acne, and skin cancer. These consequences relate to how incompatible the skincare products are to the skin of the users; its adulterated form, and the falsity attached during the advertisement.

Research Question 5: What are the solutions and recommendations that could be proffered to avoid deceptive advertising of Jenny's Glow?

It is quite surprising that despite the high prevalence of deceptive advertisement of skincare products, nothing tangible has been done to prevent the social menace. People unethically market

their products and marketing agencies seem to turn blind to the cry of the masses. These unchecked unethical marketing activities that is ravaging the nation's moral commercial value system leaves one wondering about the roles of the relevant regulatory bodies in advertising (Ukaegbu, 2020). It points out that something positive need to be done to checkmate these negative practices. The establishment of laws protecting consumers' rights was one of the ways participants reported to help curtail this act. Evidencing this, Liepinyte and Daugeliene (2012) found the relationship between solutions of deceptive advertisement and the additions of legal regulations.

Similarly, participants reported the introduction of new advertising codes to regulate the contents of adverts. This is backed up as the European Union introduced laws and regulations to protect the consumers from misleading advertisements, and also to protect them from misleading advertisements, they ensured proper education and awareness for consumers (Monika & Rasa 2012). More so, participants opined that fines should be spelt out to agencies that involve in deceptive advertising, and they also stated the importance of organizing seminars and conferences for people as regards deceptive adverts.

However, for Jenny's Glow skincare company, while some participants reported that they should be banned from operations to serve as deterrents to others engaging in deceptive advertisement, others said they should be sued by court of competent jurisdiction. In addition to this, some reported that their products need to be always checked by regulatory bodies like APCON before they put up their adverts to the public.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary

The study investigated deceptive advertising and Covenant University student's perception of Jenny's Glow skincare adverts. The findings from this study in line with the research questions revealed that participants were quite aware of the deceptive advertising that has been happening in the advertising world, and this knowledge mostly come through social media usage, which is

not surprising looking at the recent increase in social media usage across all ages. Participants also reported that they have been greatly exposed and knowledgeable about Jenny's Glow skincare product advertisements; however, their perceptions about the advertisements made were that of offensive, misleading, deceptive, and lacking facts.

Furthermore, they reported that they have purchased Jenny's Glow products as a result of the deceptive advertising, which is not surprising as the principal purpose of advertising is to draw patronage. However, on the usage of the product, majority of the participants reported they have stopped using Jenny's Glow skincare product due to different effect they perceived fake or adulterated skincare products have in the body. Some of those effects includes skin reaction, skin cancer, hyperpigmentation, discoloration and acne. In line with the deceptive advertisement adopted by Jenny's Glow skincare products, participants proffered consequences they should face. While some said they should be sued or banned, others said they should not be punished, as they were simply engaging in the dictates of advertisement. Also, some said that their adverts should be checked by advertisement regulatory bodies like APCON. Due to the negative effect of fake or adulterated skincare products to humans, participants suggested approaches that will curb deceptive advertisement. Some of their approaches include the establishment of laws protecting customers' right, establishment of new advertising codes to control contents of advertising, organizing seminars and conferences on deceptive advertising and leveling fines on advertising agencies and companies that indulge in deceptive advertising

5.2 Conclusion

The goal of advertising is to raise consumer awareness and increase patronage. However, it is not ideal to use false advertising, especially in the cosmetic/skincare sector to raise awareness and

make sales. The likelihood of misleading advertising in the skincare sector is based on the sensitive nature of the skin and the potential harm that using a product that is unsatisfactory but advertised as effective can have to the skin. This was the conclusion drawn from this study involving Jenny's Glow skincare brand, whose misleading advertisements, according to participants who had previously used the products, had a negative impact on their skin. In line with this, it is essential for the government and the current administration to implement strict regulations to restrict misleading advertising, particularly with relation to skin care products. Similar to what was stated in the study, the measures may include banning skincare companies that are discovered to use deceptive advertising to gain customers, ensuring that every advertisement for skincare products is sorted out across various platforms to ensure that it does not contain deceptive information, and imposing heavy fines on the company.

5.3 Recommendations

Advertisement is a good thing, well acceptable in the business world, as it is a means to market a product in order to increase sales. While advertising is a bit deceptive in nature, it is very wrong to be overly deceptive, especially to delicate products like skincare products. With the increase in time spent on social media across ages, social media ads have increased especially in skin care product, which is due to the need of people for “glowing skins”. Most of these ads are deceptive in nature and it is a great concern. Looking at the delicate nature of this product and the after effect as revealed by participants, it is paramount for strict measures to be put in place by government as regard to regulating advertisement, for example, putting jail term for those who engage in deceptive advertising, closure of their business, etc. Since most deceptive ads occur through social media, social media ads should be sieved in line with reports on products that

have been deemed by customers to come through deceptive advertisement, so as to help limit the number of these products in the market.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

The study was limited in the study area, as it only used students from Covenant University Ota, Ogun State; hence, it limits the tendency for the findings to be generalized. In addition, while it is evident that women are the consumers of skin care product, men have been seen to join the trend of users, especially men in private higher institutions, and this study didn't account for such men. More so, the study was limited in the participants. From the findings, some of the participants reported they are yet to make use of the Jenny's Glow skin care product, which has a way of affecting the objectivity of their responses, and subsequently the findings from the study.

5.5 Suggestions for Further Studies

Further study on this should expand in their population to include population from different schools, so as to give the findings from the study a chance of generalization. Further study on this should include male participants from private schools to get their perception on skincare products. In addition to this, future research on this should first carryout investigation to ascertain people making use of the Jenny's Glow skincare products before starting the study, to ensure that those who will participate in the study are those who are or have made use of the product. This will help ensure the validity of the study.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, D., & Saira, I. (2019). The impact of deceptive advertising on Customer loyalty: A case of telecommunication industry in Karachi, Pakistan (No. 93038). Retrieved from <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/93038/>
- Armstrong, G. M., Gurol, M. N., & Russ, F. A. (1979). Detecting and correcting deceptive advertising. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 6, 237–246.
- Aurélie, M., & Noémie, D. (2013). Deceptive advertising and consumers' reactions (Halmstad University). Retrieved from <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:627661/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

- Azeem, A., & Haq, Z. (2012). Perception towards internet advertising: A study with reference to three different demographic groups. *Global Business and Management Research: An International Journal*, 4(1), 28–45.
- Baryshnikova, E. (2017). Persuasive techniques used in marketing and advertising based on psychological factors (Saimaa University of Applied Sciences). Retrieved from https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/130959/Baryshnikova_Elizaveta.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Carrigan, M. and Attalla, A. (2001), “The myth of the ethical consumer – Do ethics matter in purchase behaviour?” *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 18 No. 7, pp. 560-77.
- Chaouachi, S., & Rached, K. (2012). Perceived deception in advertising: proposition of a measurement scale. *Journal of Marketing Research and Case Studies*, 2012, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.5171/2012.712622>
- Cleland, R. L., Koss, L. D., & Muoio, K. M. (2002). Weight-loss advertising: An analysis of current trends. Retrieved from <http://livingstrong.org/articles/weightloss.pdf>
- Comegys, C., & Hannula, M. (2006, July). Longitudinal comparison of Finnish and US online shopping behaviour among university students: The five-stage buying decision process. *Journal of Targeting, Measurement and Analysis for Marketing*, 14 (4), pp. 336-356. Copenhagen Business School.
- Darke, P. R., & Ritchie, R. J. (2007). The Defensive Consumer: Advertising Deception, Defensive Processing, and Distrust. *Journal of Marketing Research (JMR)*, 44(1), 114–127.
- Dhaliwal, A. (2016). Effect of advertisement on consumer buying behavior. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 4(09), 4501–4505. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v4i9.09>
- Eisenberg, M., John, C., & Rosemary, A. (2013). The effect of deceptive advertising on consumption of the advertised good and its substitutes: The case of over-the-counter weight loss products (No. D83). Retrieved from <http://www.nber.org/papers/w18863> European Parliament and of the Council.
- Fayyaz, N., & Amreen, L. (2015). Deceptive advertising practices and customer loyalty A case of mobile phones in Karachi, Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(31), 83–88. <https://doi.org/2222-2839>
- Gardner, D. M. (2019). “Deception in Advertising: A Conceptual Approach,” *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 39, Pp. 40-46.
- Goessl, L. (2010). How deceptive advertising hurts businesses. Retrieved from <http://ezinearticles.com>
- Hackley, C. E. (2010). Advertising and promotion: an integrated marketing communications approach. 2nd ed. Los Angeles: SAGE. 333 p. ISBN 9781849201469

- Hansen, F., Percy, L., & Hansen, M. (2004). Consumer choice behaviour- an emotional theory.
- Hastak Manoj & Mazis Michael, B. (2018). "Deception by Implication: A Typology of Truthful but Misleading Advertising and Labelling Claims," *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*.
- Heyman, S. (2016,). What makes an advertisement deceptive? Retrieved from <http://ezinearticles.com/?What-Makes-an-Advertisement-Deceptive?&id=5587937>
- Hiller, A. (2010), "Challenges in researching consumer ethics: a methodological experiment", *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, Vol. 13 No. 3, pp. 236-52.
- Hussein, s. A. (2011). Effect of deceptive advertising on consumer loyalty in telecommunication Industry of Pakistan. *Imbr*, 6.
- Langley, R. (2018). How deceptive advertising hurts businesses. Retrieved from <http://ezinearticles.com>
- Lodhi, N. F. (2015). Deceptive Advertising Practices and Customer Loyalty a Case of Mobile Phones in Karachi, Pakistan. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*. 469- 474.
- Mahjudin, M., Nurmawati, M., & Kristiawati, I. (2019). Buying behaviour pattern on online consumer (a comparison between urban and rural buyer). *Sinergy*, 9(1), 18–21.
- Malik, M. E., Ghafoor, M. M., & Iqbal, H. K. (2012). Impact of brand image and advertisement on consumer buying behavior. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 23(1), 117–122. <https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.wasj.2013.23.01.824>
- Mansoor, D., & Jalal, A. (2011). The Global Business Crisis and Consumer Behavior: Kingdom of Bahrain as a Case Study. Manama: *International Journal of Business and Management*.
- Nagody, K., Ochoa, L., Chęcinska, A., & Budziński, Ł. (2019). Persuasion in the light of research on advertising messages. Society. Integration. Education. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference, 6(May), 412. <https://doi.org/10.17770/sie2019vol6.3680>
- Official Journal of the European Union. (2005). *Directive of the European Union Journal*.
- Olson, J. C., & Dover, P. a. (1978). Cognitive Effects of Deceptive Advertising. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 15(1), 29. <http://doi.org/10.2307/3150398>
- Ray, L. (2018). What is the worst thing about deceptive advertising? azcentral.smallbusiness.chron.com.
- Solomon, M. (2009). Consumer Behaviour: A European perspective (Fourth ed.). *Pearson Education*.
- Ullah, N., & Hussain, M. (2015). Impact of unethical advertising, misleading information or deceptive advertising on customer purchasing intention with mediating effect of word of mouth: case of Pakistan. *International Journal of Innovation and Economic Development*, 1(4), 49–69. <https://doi.org/10.18775/ijied.1849-7551-7020.2015.14.2005>

- Valor, C. (2007), “The influence of information about labor abuses on consumer choice of clothes: a grounded theory approach”, *Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol. 23 Nos 7/8, pp. 675-95.
- Verigin, B. L., Meijer, E. H., & Vrij, A. (2019). The interaction of truthful and deceptive information. *Psychology, Crime & Law*, 0(0), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1068316X.2019.1669596>
- Wakeman, O. (2018.). What Is Considered Illegal Marketing in Other Countries?
- Wilson, A. (2010, January 24). How deceptive advertising hurts businesses. Retrieved from <http://www.helium.com/items/1719533-deceptiveadvertising>
www.helium.com/items/1770271-how-deceptiveadvertising-hurts-businesses
www.helium.com/items/1850474-how-deceptiveadvertising-hurts-business
- Xie, G.-X., & Boush, D. M. (2016). How susceptible are consumers to deceptive advertising claims? A retrospective look at the experimental research literature. *The Marketing Review Journal*, 11(3), 293–314.
- Zia, N. (2016). The role of advertising on consumer buying decision in Pakistan. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics, and Management Studies*, 5(4), 39–47.

APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear respondent,

I am a final year student of the Department of Mass Communication, University of Nigeria , Nsukka currently undertaking a study on ‘**DECEPTIVE ADVERTISING AND COVENANT**

UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF JENNY'S GLOW ADVERTS'. All information supplied shall be treated with utmost confidentiality. There are no special benefits attached to participating in this study. You retain your right to withdraw from this study at any point in time. By responding to this questionnaire, you authorize that your response(s) be used for research purposes only. Thank you for your cooperation.

Section A: Demographics

1. Age:
(a) 14-20 (b) 21-25 (c) 26-30 (d)30 and above
2. College:
(a) CMSS (b) COE (c) CST (d) CLDS
3. Sex:
(a) Male (b) Female
4. Level:
(a) 100 (b) 200 (c) 300 (d) 400 (e)500
5. Religion:
(a) Christian (b) Muslim (c) Others

Section B: Level of knowledge of Covenant University female students towards deceptive advertisements

6. Have you heard/seen/read about deceptive advertising?
(a) Yes (b) No (c) Not sure
7. Have you been exposed to deceptive advertising on any platform?
(a) Yes (b) No (c) Not sure
8. If your answer to question 2 is yes, on which medium did you come across such deceptive advertisement
(a) Radio (b) Television (c) Billboard (d) Social media (e) No medium
(e)Other, specify.....
9. Have you seen or heard about advertisement of skincare products?
(a) Yes (b) No (c) Not sure
10. If yes, on what medium?
(a) Radio (b) Television (c) Billboard (d)Social media
(e) I've not seen or heard about any skincare advert

Section C: Audience exposure to Jenny's Glow skincare product advertisement

Using the Likert scale, please answer questions 7 to 15 by ticking as appropriate to you:

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, U = Undecided, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

S/N		SA	A	U	D	SD
11	I have seen advertisements of Jenny’s Glow skincare product					
12	I am well knowledgeable about the advertisements of Jenny’s Glow skincare product					
13	I am very aware of the advertisements of Jenny’s Glow skincare product					

Section D: Perception of women towards Jenny’s Glow skincare advertisement

S/N		SA	A	U	D	SD
14	Jenny’s Glow advertisements are informative					
15	Jenny’s Glow advertisements are factual					
16	Jenny’s Glow advertisements are misleading					
17	Jenny’s Glow advertisements are offensive					
18	Jenny’s Glow models used for Jenny’s Glow advertisements are deceptive					
19	Jenny’s Glow uses models and influencers with already clear skin for their advertisements					
20	Adverts that claim that Jenny’s Glow will make users have permanent good skin even when they stop usage are correct					

Section E: Consequences of deceptive skincare products

21. Have you purchased Jenny’s Glow skincare product because of your exposure to the advertised product?

- (a) Yes (b) No (c) Not sure

22. Have you used Jenny’s Glow skincare product before?

- (a) Yes (b) No (c) Not sure

23. For how long did you use it?

- (a) Less than 3 months (b) 6 months (c) A year (d) More than a year (e) I've not used it before

24. Why did you stop using the product?

- (a) It was fake (b) It didn't work for me (c) I had reactions from it (d) It damaged my skin (e) I'm not using it (f) It's working for me

25. Are you currently using Jenny's Glow?

- (a) Yes (b) No (c) Not sure

26. For how long have you been using it?

- (a) Less than 3 months (b) 6 months (c) A year (d) More than a year (e) I'm not currently using it

27. Are you aware that using fake/adulterated skincare product is dangerous?

- (a) Yes (b) No (c) Not Sure

28. What are some of the dangers of using fake/adulterated skincare products

.....

- (a) Skin reaction
(b) Hyperpigmentation
(c) Discoloration
(d) Skin cancer
(e) Acne

Section F: solutions and recommendations that could be proffered to avoid deceptive advertising of Jenny's Glow

29. What are the possible solutions to avoid deceptive advertising of skincare products?

- (a) Enactment of Law protecting customer's rights
(b) Establishing new advertising codes to control contents of advertising
(c) Organizing seminars and conferences on deceptive advertising
(d) Leveling fines on advertising agencies and companies practicing deceptive advertising

30. What do you think should be done to the manufacturers of Jenny's Glow?

-
- (a) They should be sued
 - (b) They should be banned
 - (c) Nothing. They are simply advertising
 - (d) Their adverts should be checked by regulatory bodies like APCON
 - (e) I'm not familiar with the product.